



Supplementary Figure 1 – Quality assessment of microarrays.



Supplementary Figure 2 – Quality assessment of microarrays without outliers.



Supplementary Figure 3 – Determination of background intensity threshold.



Supplementary Figure 4 – Summary of mRNA abundance patterns.



Supplementary Figure 5 – AHR-core genes













Supplementary Figure 6 – Coverage estimates across targeted regions for chromosome 1 (top) to chromosome X (bottom).























Supplementary Figure 7 – Methylation summary across targeted regions for chromosome 1 (top) to chromosome X (bottom).